

Perception of Academic Librarians toward Digital Library Services in Islamabad: The Current Status and Influencing Factors

Inayat ur Rahman

Abid Hussain

<https://currentsignreview.com>

Perception of Academic Librarians toward Digital Library Services in Islamabad: The Current Status and Influencing Factors

Inayat ur Rahman

MS Scholar, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Peshawar. Email: iinayat7@gmail.com

Abid Hussain

Deputy Director Library, Institute of Strategic Studies Islamabad, Email: abidhussain@issi.org.pk

Abstract

This study examines the status and factors influencing digital library services in academic libraries in Islamabad, Pakistan. Adopting a quantitative research design, data were collected through a pretested and piloted questionnaire distributed to 300 academic librarians in Islamabad. A response rate of 93.67% (281

responses) was achieved. The data were analyzed using SPSS v27, employing independent sample t-tests and ANOVA for statistical analysis. The findings reveal a strong preference among librarians for traditional digital resources such as e-books, journals, and citation tools, while multimedia services and digital literacy programs are underutilized. Key factors influencing the adoption of digital library services include technological infrastructure, financial resources, and administrative support. These findings underscore the need for enhanced awareness, improved access, and better integration of less-utilized services to maximize the impact of digital library offerings. This research offers valuable insights for librarians, researchers, and academics, highlighting the importance of addressing technological, financial, and administrative challenges through collaborative efforts. The findings contribute to a broader understanding of digital library service adoption and provide a foundation for future research to optimize the role of academic libraries in supporting education and research.

Keywords: Digital libraries; Academic Libraries; Islamabad; Academic librarians; Digital services

Introduction

Emerging technology has brought tremendous revolutions in the 21st century. Advanced technology has been deployed across almost every sector, including defence, agriculture, business, trade, health, and education (Hussain, 2020). Significant applications of these advanced technologies, including the Internet of Things, Cloud Computing, Big Data, Blockchain, Augmented and Virtual Reality, and mobile applications, are evident in both advanced and emerging developing nations (A. Khan et al., 2014). Among them, the use of Artificial Intelligence has gained considerable attention in the last few years (Hussain, 2023). Advanced countries, such as the USA, UK, Germany, and Canada, have fully implemented the use of innovative technologies in education and library services; however, developing countries like India, Turkey, Sri Lanka, and Pakistan are still in the infancy of adopting these technologies (Ameen & Rafiq, 2009). Digital libraries are key to the modern education system, and without

them, no library can fulfil the educational needs of its patrons. Witten et al. (2009) first proposed the concept of a Digital library. He introduces the concept of a virtual library. Since the beginning of the 20th century, digital libraries have experienced rapid growth (Younus, 2014). America was the first country to take the initiative in digital libraries in the early 1990s. Hussain & Jan (2018) described a digital library as an organized group of information, a curated collection of digital items consisting of video, audio, and text, together with techniques for accessibility, preservation, organization, and management of the collection. Digital Library services (DLs) are services provided by libraries via the internet and come in various forms, such as internet access, e-books, e-journals, e-current awareness, and institutional archive repositories (Jeevan, 2004). According to Khan & Bhatti (2017), digital library services have been widely accepted in institutions of higher learning due to the benefits that advanced technology and the internet have brought. The internet has become a dynamic resource that enables libraries to offer services that meet their patrons' needs. Li (2024) describes how the internet and advanced technology, in particular, have enabled easy access to library services, providing 24/7 support, allowing users to access information from anywhere, and offering a comprehensive range of information resources for study. The study by Mubeen et al. (2021) highlighted that academic library were enabled to provide online services while patrons are out of the library. Malik & Mahmood (2014) denote that digital library services are a fundamental component of promoting research and education in higher learning institutions. The introduction of Digital library services has presented educational associations with an opportunity to search for information sources from various databases, including archival depositories (Fatima Warraich & Ameen, 2010).

The utilization of digital libraries has led to significant changes in the accessibility of library resources across both developed and developing countries (Shafiullah, 2011). The developed nations, such as the USA, Canada, and Europe, have well-established library systems, modern technological infrastructure, and large collections of materials in both digital and print formats. In contrast, developing countries, such as Bangladesh, Turkey, India, and Pakistan, face obstacles including a lack of funds for library purchasing, inadequate groundwork, limited stakeholder attention, and a shortage of resources for balanced print and digital collections (Hussain & Rafiq, 2024). Moreover, developed nations have a vast number of libraries and comfortable access to study materials, making physical access to library facilities more convenient. In contrast, developing countries face challenges related to geographic disparities and a lack of library funds, which are often concentrated in urban areas (Bhatti, 2018). With the rapid advancement of technology and the extensive use of the internet, Digital Library research has made considerable progress in Pakistan (Hussain & Jan, 2018). In the history of libraries in Pakistan, the concept of a digital library took physical shape in the last decade of the nineteenth century, when the telecommunication sector began expanding its services and the National Digital Library Program (NLDP) established computer-training centres for working librarians (Warraich & Tahira, 2009). The purpose behind its creation was to develop a system that transitioned manual libraries to digital ones for patrons. The same year, the Department of Library and Information Science at the University of Peshawar organized a conference on "Challenges in Automating the Library

Services", which helped produce Pakistan's library automation literature (Khan & Bhatti, 2017). Moreover, the Punjab University Library Science Alumni Association has contributed two publications to the literature on library education, automation, and other issues (Malik & Mahmood, 2014). The use of internet-based information resources is increasing as information technology in Pakistan advances. With the increasing popularity of using various tabs, smartphones, and the latest computers among researchers of the modern age, it is possible to access information anywhere, anytime, and work from any place (S. A. Khan & Bhatti, 2017). In Pakistan, numerous researchers have examined various aspects of digital libraries. A. Khan and Qutab (2016) noted that only a few libraries in Pakistan have taken steps toward the digitalisation of academic libraries. Scholars also indicate that many librarians are familiar with digitalization. However, considerable measures are required to establish digital libraries, including adequate funding, advanced IT skills, technical equipment, and stakeholder support (Hussain, 2025). The primary aim of this study is to investigate the culture of excellence in digital library resources and services, with a focus on librarians in academic libraries. To meet this goal, the study focuses on three objectives: 1) to assess the perceptions of academic librarians in Islamabad towards digital libraries, 2) to identify the types of digital library services provided by academic libraries in Islamabad and 3) to explore the factors influencing the implementation and utilization of digital library services in Islamabad's academic libraries.

Literature Review

The rapid development of technology has significantly transformed the global library landscape. With the proliferation of electronic resources, numerous studies have examined how students, faculty members, and researchers use digital library services to meet their research and academic needs. Similarly, numerous studies have examined digital library services from the users' perspective (Hussain & Jan, 2018). For this particular purpose, various research methods were employed, including interviews, surveys, experiments, observations, and analyses. The methods applied have yielded various conclusions, depending on users' preferences and group discipline. The study (Hussain, 2021) describes the information requirements of graduate students regarding electronic resources in Saudi Arabian universities. The review of literature denotes the development of electronic services that changed the shape of various fields especially the manual system of libraries to digitalization all over the world and particularly in Pakistan and the need for professional training for perfect digitization in Pakistan. A. Khan, (2020) examine that digital library professional's need knowledge in metadata creation, copyright management, and digital preservation. Over the last three decades, the rapid adoption of electronic resources has heightened people's demands and increased their interest in collecting data using various techniques (Hussain, 2024). The study aims to investigate the use of electronic resources, which play a crucial role in scholarly inquiry. More than 50% of the respondents used digital library services to access the information they needed. According to Paul & P. Singh (2014), the utilization of digital resources requires a certain level of technical proficiency, self-directed drive, and self-reliance. The study employed three methods to collect data, surveying users about their satisfaction, analyzing computer logs, and conducting in-person observations. The study

found that users preferred using online resources because they do not find time visiting the physical library (Hussain et al., 2025). It also suggested that digital libraries should make their online platforms easier to use. A study by Atanda et al. (2021) in Nigeria identified librarians who used digital library services in academic libraries, they considered it effective for library services.

In contrast, the adoption of digital services in Nigerian institutions is still in its early stages. Given the limited research on this topic in Pakistan, this study aimed to investigate the perceptions of the Library and Information Science (LIS) community regarding digital library services. The study examined the use and perception of digital library services in academic libraries in Pakistan, identifying the factors that hinder their adoption and the challenges associated with implementing these services.

The Digital Library Services in Pakistan require collective efforts to enhance the capacity of library professionals, as examined by Hussain & Richardson (2024). To achieve this goal, they suggested a series of training initiatives, including seminars, workshops, and conferences. These programs aim to equip librarians with the skills and knowledge to effectively adopt and use digital services in Pakistan. A separate study managed by Kolesnykova & Matveyeva (2019) in the UK's higher education sector revealed that librarians encounter numerous challenges when implementing digital library services. The primary obstacles identified include inadequate motivation, technical issues, substandard documentation, and financial constraints. A conservative environment often hinders the adoption of digital library services in academic libraries. Research by Hussain & Rafiq (2024) highlighted significant challenges, including philosophical resistance, resource constraints, limited stakeholder attention, and inadequate training. A survey of universities in Islamabad revealed that only 17 out of 23 libraries had adopted digital services, such as DSpace, to develop their repositories, citing obstacles including software selection, digitization, and organizational support. According to research by Xu & Du (2018), scholars have noted that Chinese academic libraries rely heavily on proprietary software, often favouring natively developed solutions, resulting in librarians having a limited understanding of digital library services. Despite this, many librarians in China show little enthusiasm for digital services due to misunderstandings of Information Technology threats associated with digitisation, a lack of professional skills, and inadequate vocational training. Khan et al. (2024) identified several challenges librarians in Pakistan face when adopting digital services in academic libraries in Punjab. These challenges include a lack of understanding of information technology, insufficient financial support from organizations, inadequate training workshops, and low cooperation between information technology and library organizations. Despite the growing prominence of digital library services, academic librarians continue to hold divergent views regarding their value and relevance. While some librarians perceive digital library services as value-added extensions that complement traditional physical libraries, others regard them as an inefficient use of limited library resources. Such mixed perceptions indicate a lack of consensus on whether digital library services represent a positive transformation for libraries in the twenty-first century or whether they may contribute to a decline in traditional

library utilization. This divergence highlights a critical research gap that warrants systematic empirical investigation, particularly in the context of academic libraries in Islamabad. Accordingly, the present study aims to examine academic librarians' perceptions of digital library services in Islamabad, assess the current status of these services, and identify the key factors that influence and hinder their adoption within academic institutions.

Objectives

The primary purpose of this study is to examine the culture of excellence in digital library resources and services, with a focus on librarians in academic libraries. To meet this goal, the study addresses the following objectives:

1. To assess the perceptions of academic librarians in Islamabad towards digital libraries.
2. To identify the types of digital library services provided by academic libraries in Islamabad.
3. To explore the factors influencing the implementation and utilization of digital library services in Islamabad's academic libraries.

Research Questions

1. What are the perceptions of academic librarians in Islamabad regarding digital libraries?
2. What digital library services are currently being offered by academic libraries in Islamabad?
3. What factors influence the implementation and usage of digital library services in academic libraries in Islamabad?

Methodology

The study employed a quantitative research design to collect data from academic librarians across Pakistan via an online questionnaire. The questionnaire was chosen as the primary data collection tool due to its effectiveness in reaching a geographically dispersed population and its successful use in similar studies, such as that by Hussain and Rafiq (2024). The instrument was developed based on a review of relevant literature and validated through consultation with field experts. Following their feedback, adjustments were made to enhance the questionnaire's reliability and validity. The questionnaire, designed using Google Forms, consisted of three sections. The first section gathered demographic details, including gender, age, qualifications, organizational type, designation, and years of experience. The second section consisted of closed-ended questions to assess the current status of digital libraries in Islamabad, with binary (Yes/No) responses. The third section comprised 12 items measuring factors influencing the adoption of digital libraries, using a five-point Likert scale from "Strongly Disagree" (1) to "Strongly Agree" (5). The survey was disseminated to a sample population of 300 academic librarians via platforms such as WhatsApp and email. Data collection was conducted between October 1 and December 1, 2025. Initially, 92 responses were received. After rigorous follow-

ups, 287 responses were collected, of which 281 were complete and deemed suitable for analysis. The data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 27, employing independent sample t-tests and ANOVA. The result was presented in tables.

Findings

The table provides a demographic breakdown of the study participants, categorized by gender, age, qualification, type of organization, job designation, and years of experience. Here is an explanation of the data: The participant group is predominantly male (61.2%) and younger (42.7% below 30 years of age), suggesting that younger professionals make up a significant part of the workforce. The majority of respondents work in the public sector (68.3%) and hold either a bachelor's or master's degree. Most respondents occupy the librarian role, with fewer senior (chief librarian) or junior (assistant librarian/library assistant) positions. Experience levels are diverse, but a larger proportion (29.5%) are early-career professionals with 1–5 years of experience. This demographic profile highlights a predominantly young, male workforce, oriented towards the public sector, with a strong educational foundation in Library and Information Science (LIS).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics

Constructs	Indicators	<i>f</i>	%
Gender	Male	172	61.2
	Female	109	38.8
Age	Up to 30 Years	120	42.7
	31-40 years	86	30.6
	41-50 years	60	21.4
	> 50 years	15	5.3
Qualification	BSLIS	142	50.5
	MLIS	113	40.2
	MS/MPhil	18	6.4
	Ph.D.	8	2.8
Organization	Public Sector	192	68.3
	Private Sector	89	31.7
Designation	Chief Librarian	35	12.5
	Librarian	171	60.9
	Assistant Librarian	50	17.8
	Library Assistant	25	8.9
Experience in Years	1-5 Years	83	29.5
	6-10 Years	56	19.9
	11-15 Years	70	24.9
	16-20 Years	39	13.9

More than 20 Years	33	11.7
Total	281	100%

Table 2 presents academic librarians' perceptions of digital library services. The table presented eight constructs to examine librarians' perceptions. The table shows that the highest mean score was recorded in "DLS will increase user engagement and interest in the library (Mean = 3.17, SD = 1.048), while Librarians generally agree that digital library services will boost user engagement, with moderate variability in responses. The second highest construct was " DLS offers 24/7 access to library resources for users " (Mean = 3.16, SD = 1.039), while the majority of librarians agreed to "I plan to introduce digital library services in my library (Mean = 3.15, SD = 1.021) it means that librarians have a positive inclination towards digital library services. Some librarians have their views that" DLS plays a significant role in enhancing the academic performance of the institution (Mean = 3.15, SD = 1.090). At the same time, some have expressed that "Institutions that offer DLS have a positive impact on their academic community (Mean = 3.15, SD = 1.072), which means that librarians believe that digital libraries impact academic communities. The majority of them said "I highly recommend DLS to my colleagues and peers (Mean = 3.11, SD = 1.043), which means that librarians intend to recommend the digital library services to others with consistent responses. Overall, the librarians have a generally positive perception of digital library services, with slight variability in their opinions. The responses indicate a consensus on the potential benefits of digital libraries for user engagement, accessibility, and academic performance; however, there is some diversity in views on specific aspects, such as attracting users and non-physical library engagement.

Table 2: perception of librarians toward digital Library services

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	M	SD
DLS will increase user engagement and interest in the library.	281	3.17	1.048
DLS offers 24/7 access to library resources for users.	281	3.16	1.039
I plan to introduce digital library services in my library.	281	3.15	1.021
DLS plays a significant role in enhancing the academic performance of the institution.	281	3.15	1.090
Institutions that offer DLS have a positive impact on their academic community.	281	3.15	1.072
I highly recommend DLS to my colleagues and peers.	281	3.11	1.043
DL services will help attract more users to my library.	281	3.07	1.105
Patrons who do not visit the library in person will benefit from DL services	281	3.07	1.105
Valid N (list-wise)	281		

Note: 5=Strongly Agree, 4=Agree, 3= Neutral, 2=Disagree, 1=Strongly Disagree

Table 3 presents data on the types of digital library services in academic libraries. The data show that 57 (20.3%) use access to e-books, journals, and other research papers, while 36 (12.8%) use the HEC Digital Library in Pakistan. N=39 are those academic libraries that provide access to online databases and research portals, such as JSTOR, Taylor & Francis, etc. The majority of academic libraries provide research and Citation tools, with 45 (16.0%), followed by Institutional repositories, such as theses and faculty publications, at 43 (15.3%). N=24 (8.5%) Libraries offer digital reference services, such as online chat, email, or video consultation. N=21 (7.5%) provide Open Educational Resources (OERs), while N=9 (3.2%) offer multimedia services, including digital images, videos, or audio content, in their respective libraries. Only 7 (2.5%) provide workshops and digital literacy programs in their libraries. Overall, the current status of digital library services in academic libraries is somewhat positive; however, several significant factors continue to influence their adoption across organizations.

Table 3: Types of Digital Library Services in Academic Library

Statement	<i>f</i>	%
Access to e-books, journals, research papers, etc.	57	20.3
HEC Digital Library Access	36	12.8
Online Databases and research portals, such as JSTOR, Taylor & Francis, etc.	39	13.9
Research Support and Citation Tools	45	16.0
Institutional Repositories, such as theses and faculty publications	43	15.3
Digital Reference Services, such as online chat, email, or video consultations	24	8.5
Open Educational Resources (OERs)	21	7.5
Multimedia Services such as digital images, videos, or audio resources	9	3.2
Workshops and Digital Literacy Programs	7	2.5
Total	281	100.0

Table 4 presents data on factors influencing digital library services in academic libraries, specifically the gender-wise significance of differences in librarians' perceptions of these services. An independent-samples T-test was used, and differences across a total of 12 statements were assessed at a p-value of 0.05. Among these statements, a significant difference was found in seven statements, i.e. The needs and expectations of library users like students, faculty and researchers (Male=3.33, Female=3.09), Librarians' ability to manage, support and promote the digital services (Male= 3.21, Female=3.16), Efficient organization and management of digital library resources (Male=3.24, Female=3.00), Protecting user's personal data and digital resources from cyber threats (Male=3.11, Female=3.00), support from the administration impacts digital library services (Male=3.22, Female=3.08), Poor knowledge of librarians in information technology (Male=3.21, Female=3.06), and Partnerships with other institutions for

interlibrary loans or shared database (Male=3.21, Female=2.96), rest five statements were found insignificant at the $p=0.5$).

Table 4: Factors influencing digital library services in academic libraries: Data distribution based on Male and Female with t-test

No	Statements	Male Librarians (n=172)		Female Librarians (n=109)		t-test sig.2-tailed	F-test value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1.	Technological infrastructure, such as high-speed internet and software costs	3.08	1.344	2.94	1.403	.385	.333
2.	Financial resources influence the quality of digital library services	3.44	1.130	3.23	1.060	.127	1.084
3.	The needs and expectations of library users like students, faculty and researchers	3.33	1.155	3.09	1.085	.080	4.017
4.	Librarians' ability to manage, support and promote the digital services	3.21	1.109	3.16	.964	.670	4.935
5.	Digital library services need copyright laws, licensing and fair use policies	3.19	1.078	2.88	1.069	.019*	.246
6.	Efficient organization and management of digital library resources	3.24	1.081	3.00	.903	.042*	12.319
7.	Protecting users' personal data and digital resources from cyber threats	3.11	1.162	3.00	1.009	.400	7.279
8.	Support from the administration impacts digital library services	3.22	1.100	3.08	.934	.281	6.872
9.	Ensuring that digital library services are accessible to all users	3.22	1.053	3.09	1.041	.315	1.264
10.	Poor knowledge of librarians in information technology	3.21	1.135	3.06	1.012	.265	4.748
11.	Partnerships with other institutions for interlibrary loans or shared databases	3.21	1.099	2.96	.932	.046*	10.628
12.	Growing emphasis on open access and institutional repositories	3.25	1.098	2.99	1.014	.048	3.397

Note: 5=Strongly Agree, 4=Agree, 3= Neutral, 2=Disagree, 1=Strongly Disagree

Table 5 presents the descriptive statistics for twelve statements using a one-way ANOVA test. The table presents a comparison of mean responses (M) and standard deviations (SD) across four qualification groups (BS LIS, MLIS, MS/MPhil, and Ph.D.) Additionally, the F-value and Significance (Sig.) columns are used to assess differences between groups. The results indicate that all constructs were found to be insignificant at the 0.5 level.

Table 5: Factors influencing digital library services in academic libraries: Qualification-wise data and one-way ANOVA test

No	Statements	BS LIS	MLIS	MS/MPhi	Ph.D.	F value	Sig
		N=142	N=113	1 N=18	N=8		
		M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)		
1.	Technological infrastructure, such as high-speed internet and software costs	2.94 1.354	3.09 1.379	3.06 1.259	3.63 1.685	.795	.498
2.	Financial resources influence the quality of digital library services	3.30 1.037	3.41 1.131	3.39 1.243	3.63 1.685	.381	.767
3.	The needs and expectations of library users like students, faculty and researchers	3.17 1.104	3.33 1.176	3.17 1.043	3.38 1.302	.471	.703
4.	Librarians' ability to manage, support and promote the digital services	3.15 .940	3.26 1.163	2.94 1.056	3.38 1.408	.608	.610
5.	Digital library services need copyright laws, licensing and fair use policies	3.08 1.055	3.11 1.121	2.89 .900	2.75 1.488	.448	.719
6.	Efficient organization and management of digital library resources	3.18 1.013	3.16 .969	2.83 1.249	3.25 1.389	.635	.593
7.	Protecting users' personal data and digital resources from cyber threats	3.09 1.136	3.07 1.075	2.67 .970	3.50 1.195	1.224	.301
8.	Support from the administration impacts digital library services	3.13 .984	3.19 1.101	2.94 .938	3.75 1.282	1.191	.314
9.	Ensuring that digital library services are accessible to all users	3.14 1.056	3.15 1.063	3.22 .878	3.88 .991	1.274	.284
10.	Poor knowledge of librarians in information technology	3.22 1.073	3.08 1.111	3.00 1.085	3.38 1.188	.567	.637
11.	Partnerships with other institutions for interlibrary loans or shared databases	3.09 1.051	3.12 1.019	3.17 1.098	3.25 1.282	.085	.968
12.	Growing emphasis on open access and institutional repositories	3.19 1.104	3.13 1.031	3.00 1.029	3.00 1.309	.244	.866

Note: 5=Strongly Agree, 4=Agree, 3= Neutral, 2=Disagree, 1=Strongly Disagree

Discussions

This paper aims to achieve three objectives: to examine librarians' perceptions, services, and influencing factors that hinder digital library services in Islamabad. The first objective of this research was "To assess the perceptions of academic librarians in Islamabad towards digital libraries." This objective is based on eight constructs. A five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree), was used to measure academic librarians' perceptions

of digital library services. The constructs align with the study by Jabeen et al. (2017), which surveyed university libraries in Nanjing, China, and found that librarians are inclined toward digital library services at Nanjing universities. Xia (2003) surveyed New Zealand academic libraries, suggesting that librarians in these institutions perceive digital libraries as meeting the basic needs of their patrons and are striving to connect more users with their digital libraries. Warraich & Tahira (2009) surveyed Pakistani librarians and found that librarians in Pakistan are not fully aware of digital libraries, particularly those offered by higher education institutions. The study suggested that librarians should explore digital databases and guide library users. This research examines librarians' perceptions of digital libraries and serves as a guiding principle for librarians in Islamabad and beyond.

The second objective of the research is "To identify the types of digital library services provided by academic libraries in Islamabad." Digital library services vary from library to library, as this study encompasses the current status of digital library services in the academic environment of Islamabad. A similar study was conducted by Ahmad et al. (2023) among 135 academic librarians in Punjab, Pakistan, and found that the majority were not fully aware of digital libraries. Towolawi (2018) also surveyed Nigeria and found that librarians there use different types of digital library services; some consider open-access digital libraries, such as those provided by Google, while others view digital libraries as paid databases purchased by the organisation. In the present study, we inquired about the digital library services librarians offer. Some mentioned using the HEC Digital Library, while others stated that they provide internal repository services, and others rely more on open digital libraries (Hussain, 2025c).

The third objective of this research is "To explore the factors influencing the implementation and utilization of digital library services in Islamabad's academic libraries. For this question, 12 constructs were developed using a five-point Likert scale to measure factors influencing digital library services in Pakistan. Owing into mind the study of Xu & Du (2018), which was conducted a study in Chinese universities and found that the majority of librarians in Chinese universities say that a few burning factors are a lack of technical knowledge of librarians, lack of finance from the organization for the libraries, and low intentions of library staff towards the adoption of digital library services (Hussain, 2025). Similarly, Mubeen et al. (2021) surveyed librarians in Pakistan and found that the majority relied more on printed materials than on digital libraries. Similarly, the slow internet speed and a lack of information literacy are two factors that affect the adoption of digital libraries. They conducted a similar study. This paper highlights various aspects and explores how librarians in Islamabad can utilize it as a guideline for adopting digital library services.

Conclusion

The present study offers a deeper understanding of digital library services and the factors that influence their utilization in academic libraries in Islamabad. The findings of this study reveal that librarians prefer traditional digital library services, such as e-book and e-journal provision

and citation management tools. Additionally, the study highlights several other services, such as digital literacy programs and multimedia resources, that remained underutilized in the academic libraries of Islamabad. The study highlights three critical factors that affect the utilization of digital library services such as administrative support, technological infrastructure, and financial resources. Furthermore, the study's findings also reveal a pressing need to increase the number of digital library services in academic settings. For this, collective efforts are required from academic institutions, policymakers, and librarians to enhance awareness through workshops, seminars, and conference programs. The study contributes to a broader discourse on the adoption of digital library services. Further research can be conducted to expand the role of emerging technologies and user engagement strategies in enhancing the optimization of digital library services in Pakistan.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the present research proposes the following recommendations.

1. Academic institutions should develop a digital library service by formulating clear policies. It is the responsibility of university leadership to recognize the digital library services as a strategic component of teaching, learning and research activities.
2. Academic institutions should enhance their ICT infrastructure and funding for high-speed internet, digital platforms, licensed databases, and system maintenance to ensure effective digital library services.
3. Capacity building and continuous professional development are key factors in establishing digital library services. It is the responsibility of academic leadership to organize regular training programs and workshops to enhance librarians' technical competencies in managing and sustaining the digital library services.
4. Although some universities have launched traditional digital library services (E-books and E-journals). It is their responsibility to enhance institutional repositories, multimedia resources, digital reference services, and digital literacy programs to meet the evolving needs of their patrons.
5. Digital library services are specifically for the users within academic libraries. The majority of academic institutions have HEC digital library services; however, there are ongoing user awareness and engagement issues with these services. Academic librarians should actively promote digital library services through awareness campaigns, orientation programs, and user-centred outreach to increase their use, especially among those who do not have time to visit their libraries personally.
6. As gender-based differences were observed across several institutions, these are influencing factors in digital library services. Academic librarians should ensure equitable participation in the management of digital library services.
7. Future research directions are key factors for enhancing digital library services in academic institutions in Islamabad particularly and generally in Pakistan, by exploring the integration of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, cloud-based

Journal for Current Sign

Online ISSN (3006-1504)

Print ISSN (3006-1490)

systems in digital libraries, and big data analytics. Researchers can further explore the scope of digital library services in Islamabad.

References

- Ahmad, A., Asad, I. H., & Khan, H. (2023). Development of Institutional Repository in Public Sector University Libraries of Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Information Management and Practices*, 3(1). <https://journals.iub.edu.pk/index.php/jimp/article/view/1895>
- Ahmad, S., Reba, A., Khan, R., Ahmad, S. M., & Din, J. U. (2021). Perceptions of Postgraduate Research Scholars about Using Digital Library Resources: A Case Study of District Peshawar. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 0_1-17.
- Ameen, K., & Rafiq, M. (2009). Development of digital libraries in Pakistan. In *Handbook of research on digital libraries: Design, development, and impact* (pp. 482–491). IGI Global. <https://www.igi-global.com/chapter/handbook-research-digital-libraries/19913>
- Arif, M., & Mahmood, K. (2012). The changing role of librarians in the digital world: Adoption of Web 2.0 technologies by Pakistani librarians. *The Electronic Library*, 30(4), 469–479. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02640471211252184>
- Atanda, A. D., Owolabi, K. A., & Ugbala, C. P. (2021). Professional competence and attitudes of library personnel towards digital services in selected university libraries in Nigeria. *Digital Library Perspectives*, 37(3), 209–222.
- Bhatti, R. (2018). Barriers in Developing Digital Competencies: Exploring Practical Solutions for. University libraries of Pakistan. *Journal of Library and Information Science* (26(2). 17–28.
- Bisma, B., Nahida, N., & Loan, F. A. (2019). National Digital Library of India: An overview. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2019. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=5975&context=libphilprac/1000>
- Butt, K., Khan, A., & Ahmad, P. (2022). The Journey of Digital Library Establishment in Pakistan: A Systematic Literature Review. *Library Philosophy & Practice*.
- Byrne, A. (2003). Digital libraries: Barriers or gateways to scholarly information? *The Electronic Library*, 21(5), 414–421.
- Chowdhury, G. G. (2016). How to improve the sustainability of digital libraries and information Services? *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67(10), 2379–2391. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23599>
- Fatima Warraich, N., & Ameen, K. (2010). Perceptions of LIS professionals regarding the use of Pakistan National Digital Library databases. *The Electronic Library*, 28(1), 108–121.
- Hurst, S. (2013). Current trends in UK university libraries. *New Library World*, 114(9/10), 398–407.
- Hussain, A. (2020). Cutting edge: Technology's impact on library services. In *Innovations in the designing and marketing of information services* (pp. 16–27). IGI Global. <https://www.igi-global.com/chapter/cutting-edge/238161>
- Hussain, A. (2020). Industrial Revolution 4.0: Implication to libraries and librarians. *Library Hi Tech News*, 37(1), 1–5.
- Hussain, A. (2021). Uses of blockchain technologies in library services. *Library Hi Tech News*,

- 38(8), 9–11.
- Hussain, A. (2022). Review of augmented reality in academic and research libraries. *Library Hi Tech News*, 39(9), 23–25.
- Hussain, A. (2022). Use of WhatsApp technology in library services: A case study of National Defence University Library, Islamabad, Pakistan. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1–11.
- Hussain, A. (2023). Use of artificial intelligence in the library services: Prospects and challenges. *Library Hi Tech News*, 40(2), 15–17. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHTN-11-2022-0125>
- Hussain, A. (2024). Unlocking the potential of ChatGPT in academic libraries. *IP Indian Journal of Library Science and Information Technology*, 9(2), 88–97. <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.ijlsit.2024.015>
- Hussain, A., & Jan, S. U. (2018). Awareness of Web 2.0 technology in the academic libraries: An Islamabad perspective. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1–13.
- Hussain, A., & Jan, S. U. (2018). User perception of electronic resources and services in the National Defence University Library, Islamabad, Pakistan. *Pakistan Library & Information Science Journal*, 49(3), 58–68.
- Hussain, A., Khan, A., & Ahmad, P. (2024). Library management models: A review and direction for future research. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/GKMC-08-2023-0309/full/html>
- Hussain, A., & Rafiq, M. (2024). Perceptions of Academic Librarians toward Open Source Library System (OSLS): Case Study of Pakistan. *Science & Technology Libraries*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0194262X.2023.2286649>
- Hussain, A., & Richardson, J. (2024). Awareness of Pakistani academic librarians towards communication skills: Barriers and benefits. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/gkmc-06-2024-0373/full/html>
- Hussain, A., & Shahid, R. (2022). Impact of big data on library services: Prospects and challenges. *Library Hi Tech News*, 000–000.
- Hussain, A. (2025). Examining Artificial Intelligence (AI) Literacy among University Library Professionals in Pakistan: The Case of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Available at SSRN 5278625. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5278625
- Hussain, A. (2025). Redefining Libraries in 21st Century: Transformative Roles for Bridging Research, Education, Technology and Society. National Book Foundation.
- Hussain, A. (2025). Unlocking the Potential of Artificial Intelligence in Academic Libraries. In E. P. Dadios (Ed.), *AI - Ethical and Legal Challenges*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.1008234>
- Hussain, A., Rafiq, M., & Ahmad, R. (2025). Digital Skills Competencies Among University Librarians in Islamabad, Pakistan. *New Review of Academic Librarianship*, 1–19.
- Jabeen, M., Qinjian, Y., Yihan, Z., Jabeen, M., & Imran, M. (2017). Usability Study of Digital Libraries: An Analysis of User Perception, Satisfaction, Challenges, and Opportunities at University Libraries of Nanjing, China. *Library Collections, Acquisitions, & Technical Services*, 40(1–2), 58–69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649055.2017.1331654>

- Jain, P. K., & Babbar, P. (2006). Digital libraries initiatives in India. *The International Information & Library Review*, 38(3), 161–169.
- Jeevan, V. K. J. (2004). Digital library development: Identifying sources of content for developing countries with special reference to India. *The International Information & Library Review*, 36(3), 185–197.
- Kenton, J., & Blummer, B. (2010). Promoting Digital Literacy Skills: Examples from the Literature and Implications for Academic Librarians. *Community & Junior College Libraries*, 16(2), 84–99. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02763911003688737>
- Khan, A. (2020). Digital information literacy skills of Pakistani librarians: Exploring supply-demand mismatches, adoption strategies and acquisition barriers. *Digital Library Perspectives*, 36(2), 167–189.
- Khan, A., & Ahmed, S. (2013). The impact of digital library resources on scholarly communication: Challenges and opportunities for university libraries in Pakistan. *Library Hi Tech News*, 30(8), 12–29.
- Khan, A., Ahmed, S., & Masrek, M. N. (2014). Scholars' Satisfaction With Digital Library Collection and Gaps in the Provision of Effective Information Resources and Services: A Pakistani Perspective. *Journal of Electronic Resources Librarianship*, 26(4), 250–267. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1941126X.2014.971671>
- Khan, A., & Khan, F. (2014). Implementation of Digital Reference Services in Pakistani Libraries: A Descriptive and Critical Annotated Bibliographical Guide. *Pakistan Library & Information Science Journal*, 45(2).
- Khan, A., & Qutab, S. (2016). Understanding research students' behavioural intention in the adoption of digital libraries: A Pakistani perspective. *Library Review*, 65(4/5), 295–319.
- Khan, S. A., & Bhatti, R. (2017). Digital competencies for developing and managing digital libraries: An investigation from university librarians in Pakistan. *The Electronic Library*, 35(3), 573–597. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EL-06-2016-0133>
- Kolesnykova, T., & Matveyeva, O. (2019). An analysis of digital library publishing services in Ukrainian universities. *Evidence-Based Library and Information Practice*, 14(4), 52–71.
- Malik, A., & Mahmood, K. (2014). Readiness for digital reference service (DRS) in university libraries: A survey in the Punjab, Pakistan. *Information Development*, 30(2), 181–188. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0266666913489700>
- Masreka, M. N., & Husseinb, A. (2021). Intention to adopt mobile applications services: A study among Pakistani academic librarians. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 15(3), 38–54.
- Mubeen, I., Soroya, S. H., & Mahmood, K. (2021). Identifying the factors influencing digital library use among research students: A case of National Digital Library of Pakistan. *Digital Library Perspectives*, 37(3), 192–208.
- Parida, B. (2004). *Emergence of digital library services in India*. <https://ir.inflibnet.ac.in:8443/ir/handle/1944/334>
- Paul, S., & P. Singh, S. (2014). Digitization initiatives and special libraries in India. *The Electronic Library*, 32(2), 221–238.

- Shafiullah, M. F. (2011). Digital library services of the Higher Education Commission in Pakistan. *Pakistan Library and Information Science Journal*, 42(2), 12–28.
- Sheaffer, K., & Vinson, C. (2023). Technology equipment lending in an academic library: Understanding patron usage and proficiency through quantitative assessment. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 49(2), 102655. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2022.102655>
- Shem, M. (2015). Digital Library Education: Global Trends and Issues. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(17), 66–70.
- Sherpa, M. D. D. (2021). *Need of knowledge management in digital library: Skills, role and barriers*. <https://www.ijim.in/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Vol-5-Issue-XII-Paper3-22-27-Mrs.-Dawa-Doma-Sherpa-NEED-OF-KNOWLEDGE-MANAGEMENT.pdf>
- Si, L., Zeng, Y., Guo, S., & Zhuang, X. (2019). Investigation and analysis of research support services in academic libraries. *The Electronic Library*, 37(2), 281–301.
- Towolawi, K. (2018). A Survey of Awareness and Perception of Digital Library Services in Nigeria. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 180(24), 14–21. <https://doi.org/10.5120/ijca2018916564>
- Warraich, N. F., & Tahira, M. (2009). HEC National Digital Library: Challenges and opportunities for LIS professionals in Pakistan. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2009, 1–10.
- Witten, I. H., Bainbridge, D., & Nichols, D. M. (2009). *How to build a digital library*. Morgan Kaufmann.
- Xia, W. (2003). Digital Library Services: Perceptions and Expectations of User Communities and Librarians in a New Zealand Academic Library. *Australian Academic & Research Libraries*, 34(1), 56–70. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00048623.2003.10755218>
- Xu, F., & Du, J. T. (2018). Factors influencing users' satisfaction and loyalty to digital libraries in Chinese universities. *Computers in Human Behaviour*, 83, 64–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.01.029>
- Younus, M. (2014). *Digital reference services in university libraries of Pakistan* [PhD Thesis, Loughborough University]. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/288377497.pdf>